

THE APPLICATION OF POSITRON ANNIHILATION METHODS FOR INVESTIGATION AND TESTING OF COMPOSITES

S.A. Tishin¹, V.A. Tishin², V.N. Kestelman³

¹*Institute of Electronics, Academy of Science, 10 Alleya Paradov, Tashkent, 700000, Uzbekistan*

²*Mitsar-A Inc., 59 Parkentskaya Street, Tashkent, 700070, Uzbekistan*

³*KVN International Inc., 632 Jamie Circle, King of Prussia, Pa 19406, USA*

SUMMARY: It is shown that the use positron annihilation methods allowed to investigate the properties of components and composites with different fillers and matrix. The methods was also used for analysis of microdefects in disordered polymers, for study of polymer modification and for diagnostics of polymer composites.

KEYWORDS: positron annihilation, microdefects, polymer modification, silica powder, diagnostics, microstructure, phase transition, diffusion

INTRODUCTION

The purposes of this article are: 1) to analyze the mechanism of formation and decay of a positronium atom in fine powder silicas and to use the positron annihilation for study of structure peculiarities, 2) to use positron annihilation for diagnostics of polymer composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Investigation of Fine Power Silicas Composites

The surface modification of fine powder silicas by the organic compounds allows us to use them as selective adsorbents, catalysts or active fillers for polymer systems [1,2].

The complicated structure of the surface layer of silica modified by inoculated organic and inorganic groups is still very interesting topic [3-12].

Positron annihilation experiments

The observation of positron annihilation (PA) has been conducted by two principal methods: measuring the life time (LT) and spectra and the angular correlation of annihilation radiation (ACAR), to which has been added the measurement of probability of a three-photon annihilation (TFA). The application of a set of experimental measuring techniques is a principle particular to this work, as the interpretation of complicated polycomponent annihilation spectra in fine powder substances is difficult. The comparison of LT, ACAR and

TFA results permits us to define more precisely the annihilation mechanism and consequently to make well founded conclusions about the properties of the substances under study.

Mathematical treatment of spectra has been carried out by means of the computer programs POSITRON FIT, RESOLUTION and ACAR FIT [13].

Samples

Fine modified silicas [2] obtained by substitution of surface groups by organic compounds of a different nature as well as alumo- and titanoaerosil samples obtained by combined high-temperature hydrolysis of titanium (or aluminum) vapour and silicon chlorides have been investigated. Some experimental characteristics are in Table 1.

Table 1: Specific surface area (S), structure and concentration of inoculated groups (a) of fine powder silica samples.

Grades of Silica	Structure of Surface	$S \cdot 10^{-3}, m^2/kg$	a, nmol/g
Aerosil, A-175	$\equiv Si-OH$	175	0.30-0.35*
Aerosil, A-300	$\equiv Si-OH$	300	0.60*
Aerosil, modified by diethyleneglycol, ADEG	$\equiv Si-O-CH_2-CH_2-OH$	300	0.70-0.80
Aminoethoxyaerosil, AEA	$ \begin{array}{c} O-C_2H_5 \\ \\ \equiv Si-O-CH_2-CH_2-NH_2 \\ \\ O-C_2H_5 \end{array} $	300	0.70
Aminopropylaerosil, APA	$\equiv Si-O-Si-O-(CH_2)_3-NH_2$	300	0.50
Butosil, B-2	$\equiv Si-O-(CH_2)_3-CH_3$	300	0.70
Titanoaerosil, TAS-20	$\equiv Si-O-Ti \equiv$	108	0.20**
Alumoaerosil, A-A-8	$\equiv Si-O-Al \equiv$	256	0.08**

* Concentration of silanol groups

** Mass part of titanium and aluminium oxides

Experimental data

The quick positrons emitted from the source ^{22}Na are thermalized in the volume of silica microparticles. The thermal positrons can annihilate by means of quasi-elastic collisions with atoms and molecules (free positrons) and by means of formation of localized states in structure defects of atomic size.

An effective mechanism of slowing down positrons at energies of a few eV is the formation of a positronium atom - bound state of positron and electron. With spin orientation it is possible to form para-positronium p-Ps (self-annihilation time 0.125 ns 2γ -decay), and ortho-positronium o-Ps (self-annihilation time of 140 ns, 3γ -decay in vacuum). The ratio of probability of the formation of para- and ortho-Ps is 1:3 because of different statistical weights. However, as a result of Ps interaction with atoms and molecules of the media, Ps characteristics (LT and its kinetic energy) are changed.

Characteristics of positronium are traditionally of great interest for studying fine powder samples of silicas [3-12]. Changes of o-Ps LT and the formation of a narrow component of the ACAR curve can be detected easily.

The experimental results of LT, ACAR spectra and of TFA probability are in Tables 2-3. The computer-fitted results of a four-component analysis with a fixed value of the shortest-lived component ($\tau_1 = 0.120$ ns) and associated similarly [12] with annihilation of p-Ps are listed in the Tables. Annihilation characteristics for the silica samples changed with dispersion degree and with the state of the microparticle surface. The most considerable changes have been observed for aluminosilicates and titanosilicates. However, samples modified by organic combinations are also clearly different in comparison with the experimental error by its annihilation spectra.

Table 2: Characteristics of lifetime positron spectra: life time (τ_s , τ_I , τ_L) and intensities (I_s , I_I , I_L) of short-lived, intermediate and long-lived components.

Samples	τ_s ± 0.006 ns	τ_I ± 0.07 ns	τ_L ± 1.5 ns	I_s ± 0.70 %	I_I ± 0.70 %	I_L ± 0.18 %
A-175	0.409	1.73	70.9	78.11	10.12	11.77
A-300	0.417	2.14	69.0	79.54	6.38	14.08
ADEG	0.421	1.71	66.6	69.95	18.20	11.86
AEA	0.419	1.87	66.7	78.83	10.16	11.01
APA	0.424	1.93	69.1	76.70	11.35	11.95
B-2	0.417	1.95	67.3	74.15	9.95	15.90
TAS-20	0.366	1.37	71.1	95.89	2.02	2.09
A-A-B	0.429	1.88	69.0	89.35	4.89	5.67
Amorphous quartz	0.429	1.62	-	58.59	41.41	-

Among the three time components well distinguished for silica powder the origin of the longest-lived component is studied the most [3, 4, 6, 8]. That component is formed as a result of ortho-positron annihilation in the volume between silica grains [3-6, 9]. The decay in high vacuum occurs not only by means of 3γ -self-annihilation but also by means of 2γ -annihilation [11, 12]. Because of the interactions with the microparticle surface LT of o-Ps is shortened up to 130 ns [11]. If the pores between the particles are filled up with the gas, LT

of oPs decreased more as a result of interactions with gas molecules. In this work the measurements are carried out in air, for which it is known [9] that the most important mechanism of LT shortening is ortho-para conversion at an in-elastic collision of a positronium with a molecule of oxygen.

As a result of conversion, LT of o-Ps in the pores is decreased up to 70 ns and as it can be seen from Table 2 LT does not depend practically on specific surface area and surface state. The state and the particle surface are very important. The changes of intensities of positronium components of annihilation spectra are in Table 2. The samples with different surfaces are united in two groups. The first group is the silica on the base of A-300 with different organophylic surfaces. First, it should be noted that an increase in intensity of o-Ps annihilation in the pores between grains for butosil (B-2) takes place in this group. A corresponding increase of the intensity of the narrow component of the ACAR curve and of the TFA probability for this sample has been observed. The similar change in angle spectra have been found earlier [10] at the dehydration of the surface of fine powder silicas. So it can be proposed, that most values of I_L, I_N and $P_{3\gamma}$ in B-2 are due to hydrophobic properties of its surface.

Table 3: Total probability of positronium formation (P_o), intensity of narrow component of angular distribution (I_N^1) obtained by characteristics of positron lifetime and probability of three-photons annihilation ($P_{3\gamma}$), as well as intensities of intermediate component (I_I) normalized to the sum of ortho-positroniums components (I_I+I_L) and probability of three-photons annihilation.

Samples	$P_{3\gamma}+0.1$ %	$P_o+1.2$ %	$I_N^1+0.5$ %	$\frac{I_I}{I_I+I_L}$	$\frac{I_I}{P_{3\gamma}}$
A-175	7.3	30.7	19.4	0.46	1.37
A-300	8.5	30.3	21.7	0.31	0.75
ADEG	6.0	40.7	22.0	0.60	3.03
AEA	6.0	28.5	18.1	0.48	1.70
AAPA	6.8	31.5	19.7	0.49	1.67
B-2	10.1	36.9	25.1	0.39	0.88
TAS-20	1.5	5.7	2.5	0.47	1.33
A-A-8	3.3	16.5	9.2	0.47	1.92

An alternative possible reason of the effect observed is the change of probability of positronium formation with the chemical nature of inoculated groups. In this group the decrease of the positronium quantity with modification by polar amino-containing groups is observed. The polarity is higher, the probability of positronium formation on the surface is lower and less positronium atoms escaped in the pores between the particles. Such a

correlation of probability of positronium formation with polarity is observed, for example, in polymers [14].

A special position is occupied by the sample modified by diethylenglycol (ADEG) for which I_L and $P_3\gamma$ have the lower values, but maximum value of I_I . This effect is caused by the largest probability of formation and capture of positronium atoms on the surface among silicas studied. This sample is likely to be characterized by the formation of a more complicated and extended structure of the surface layer formed by groups inoculated and by water molecules absorbed. Additional hydration of the ADEG surface is connected with the presence of the mobile hydroxyl end group and occurs in decreasing the τ_1 value which approaches to that characteristic of annihilation in water and in increasing I_I because of a larger probability of positronium formation in water.

In accordance with [3, 9, 11], the decrease of I_L , $P_3\gamma$ values with the increase of grain size (the samples of A-175 and A-300) is observed. However, the anomalously great decrease of contribution of positronium components to spectra for alumo- and titanoaerosills can not be explained by the changes of particle discursiveness (Table 1).

In our opinion the effect observed can be connected with the decay of positronium atoms while passing the surface on acid centers or according to the model of formation of positronium on the surface with the high potential barrier for the electron escape. For the latter the inhibition of positronium formation is connected with the energy limitation of the possibility of forcing out electron from the surface, necessary for the formation of positronium.

There is no common opinion on the origin of the intermediate component of LT in the fine powder silica samples. Earlier there were ideas more theoretically and experimentally substantiated according to which the positronium formation occurs inside the particles and then as a result of diffusion a number of o-Ps atoms can come out into a free volume between particles. The escape probability can be determined by the microparticle radius, LT and coefficient of positronium diffusion [3]. Later it was experimentally found that the intensity of the intermediate component (and the intensity of narrow positronium component of ACAR) is varied depending on the state of the particle surface [5, 8, 11, 12]. In addition, it should be noted that the LT value observed in the amorphous quartz (1,1-1,8 ns) is less than the τ_1 value registered in the experiments and that the τ_1 value depends on the surface area and state (Table 2).

Thus, there are reasons to suppose that the intermediate component is due to both annihilation inside the particles and annihilation on its surface. Inner centers of capture are more likely to be formed on the boundary of primary submicroparticles (by the size of 10 nm), adhering during high-temperature hydrolysis with the formation of the secondary particle-agglomerates [1]. Hence, the characteristics of the intermediate component of the LT spectrum are an integral sum from positronium annihilation on the internal (difficult for the other larger atomic and molecular probes) and external surface of silica microparticles.

In accordance with the diffusion model the increase of particles size in alumo- and titanoaerosills must lead to the increase of a contribution to the intermediate component (annihilation in volume defects of packing of molecular size). Values of I_I and I_L are substantially decreased for those samples. There is no reason to suppose that the whole effect of inhibition can be explained by the changes of the Ore gap boundaries or by parameters of a

positronium spur as disperse samples of Al_2O_3 , e.g., are characterized by a not lower probability of the positronium formation [6, 9]. So there are also reasons to connect the considerable decrease of I_1 in those samples with the influence of hidden surface - with the Ps decay on acid centers on the internal boundary of submicroparticles.

The comparison of positronium LT with the TFA probability permits us to estimate the total probability P_o of positronium formation in the samples studied. The values of P_o are in Table 3. It can be seen that the changes of probability of Ps formation differ from the character of the changes of I_L , I_N and $P_{3\gamma}$ values. That underlines the differences noted above, in annihilation mechanisms, depending on the surface state or molecular inclusions of metal oxide.

The contribution of annihilation on the surface can be estimated by the I_1 value normalized to the total intensity of o-Ps components in the LT spectra $I_1/(I_1 + I_L)$ or by taking into account that 3 -decay of o-Ps is not completely registered by LT spectra and that the TFA probability gives the more complete information about positronium annihilation in free volume between the particles, to $P_{3\gamma}$. Values normalized are in Table 3. According to that parameter titanioaerosils and butosil are characterized by the least surface annihilation contribution and ADEG by the most one. Those results are approximate because the small contribution of volume annihilation is not subtracted from the I_1 value.

The values of the intensity of the narrow component ACAR are also listed in Table 3. Estimates have been obtained by approximation, that three annihilation channels contribute to a narrow component: (1) self-annihilation of p-Ps in pores - as precise measurements [8] have shown the width of this component is determined by the energy of positronium emitted from the silica surface which is not thermalized within the short time of a para-state lifetime; (2) annihilation of p-Ps in defects and on the particle surface - this component must be approximately one third from I_1 value of lifetime spectrum and also, as the first one, can not be very narrow (because of the formation of the localized state); (3) annihilation as a result of ortho-para conversion on oxygen, which gives the more narrow distribution because a part of positronium is thermalized by elastic collision with walls and gas molecules.

The values obtained are in a good agreement with the results of angular spectrum measurements (Table 3). The experimental data qualitatively justify the annihilation model suggested. The exceeding of the value calculated by 2-3% in comparison with the experimental one can be explained by the inadequacy of a three Gaussian model by which the angular spectrum has been approximated.

POSITRON DIAGNOSTICS OF POLYMER COMPOSITES

The correlation of the probability of positronium formation and its annihilation characteristics with microstructure properties of polymer composites is discussed. The results obtained allow to make the conclusion about efficiency of this method at analysis microdefects in disordered polymer (5...20 nm) which are inaccessible or difficult for the other analytical methods.

Observation of Phase Transition in Thermoelastoplasts

The present work investigates the temperature dependencies of positronium component lifetime τ_L butadien-sturene thermoelastoplasts (TEP) and in samples of polybutadiene (PB)

and polystyrene (PS) [15]. Unique technological properties of TEP make it necessary to study their microstructure by different methods.

Commercial samples of styrene-butadiene-styrene block copolymers, obtained by the method of solution polymerization on the presence of lithium-organic compounds, were investigated. The mass content of styrene in the TEP was 25%.

It is known that butadiene styrene TEPs possess a two phases segregation structure. According to mechanical factors TEPs are similar to laces filled elastomers. Comparing $\tau_L=f(T)$ dependencies for these samples it should be noted that in TEPs there are two fractures one of which corresponds to the glass transition of polybutadiene matrix (-100°C) and the second one to the glass transition of polystyrene blocks (+90°C). In the temperature dependence in PB, PS there is one glass transition.

The T_g for both PS and PB blocks increases in comparison to T_g of corresponding polymers. This effect cannot be explained by mutual penetration of PB and PS phases. The T_g increase in PS is connected with the formation of the more ordered structure in microblocks PS in TEP. The T_g increase for PB blocks can be explained by the influence of the intermediated phase.

Annihilation in Polymers with Carbon-black

Annihilation spectra in samples of polybutadiene rubber with different content (up to 50 mass fraction) and type of carbon (the mean of particle diameter being 30 and 180 nm for PM-100 and PM-15 types, respectively) were measured [16].

The changes of intermediate and long-time components intensity (I_d) of the time spectrum depending in the content and type of carbon black were found. I_d change in the spectrum filled by PM-15 is well described by the Eqn.1 obtained under assumption of additive contribution of positron annihilation in the filled and polymer:

$$I_d = I_d^0 \left(1 - \frac{KC}{1 + KC}\right); \quad K = \frac{V_n}{1 - V_n}; \quad C = \frac{a_n}{a_p} = 2.45 \quad (1)$$

where: I_d^0 is the intensity of long-time component in pure rubber; V_n is the filled volumetric fraction; a_n , a_p are positron absorption coefficients in a filler and a polymer respectively.

Concentration dependence I_d for the samples filled by highly dispersed black PM-100 is also well described by the above ratio. In this case $C = 5.50$, i.e. twice as high as additive value. Increase of C can be due to positronium atom trapping by black particles (in samples with PM-15 trapping is negligible as black concentration does not exceed $2 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$).

The efficiency of positron diagnostics application for the study of elastomeric matrix in the systems with carbon-black content is determined by the ratio of diffusion length and the distance between the trapping centers, i.e. carbon particles. In the case of sample filling by carbon black of PM-100 type diffusion length is 15-30 nm taking into account high concentration of particles even for low levels of filling, the diffusion effects in these samples can be easily found. For samples with PM-15 carbon black trapping effects can be observed under content of 0.7-0.8 mass fraction.

Observation of modification of epoxides

The temperature dependencies of the rate of counting in maximum of angular distribution of annihilation photons in samples of epoxipiperidine polymer (sample 1) modified by silicon rubber (sample 2) and blocked diisocyanates (sample 3) have been measured [17].

Two temperature transitions related to glass transition in densely packed globular (T_g^2) and loosened interglobular regions (T_g^1) have been discovered. The position and intensity of transitions are found to be largely dependent on the modifiers availability.

The maximum has been observed at temperature range $T_g^1+50^\circ\text{C}$ on temperature curves and it can be caused by the relaxation of microcavities [18]. The relaxation effect occurs at temperature $T_g^2+80^\circ\text{C}$ too.

Table 4: Temperatures ($^\circ\text{C}$) of glass transitions and relaxation maximums in epoxide polymers.

Samples	T_g^1	T_g^2	T_n^1	T_n^2
1	42	130	87	-
2	35	115	82	185
3	37	93	83	170

On the basis of the results obtained it may be concluded the improvement of physical and mechanical properties at modification caused not only by increasing the facing density but by lowering the degree of heterogeneity structure of epoxide composites, as well.

CONCLUSION

Positron annihilation can be widely used as sensitive tool for the investigation of components and their interaction in composites, for study of physic-mechanical properties and structure of composites and polymers for diagnostics of polymer composites.

REFERENCES

1. Iler R.K, The chemistry of silica, Wiley-Interscience Publication, London 1979.
2. Chuiko A.A. and Gorlov U.I., Khimiya poverchnosty kremnezema, Naukova dumka, Kiev, 1991.
3. Brandt W. and Paulin R., Phys.Rev.Lett., 1968, # 21, pp. 193-201.
4. Steld F.R. and Varlashkin P.G., Phys.Rev.B, 1972, #5, pp. 4265-4269.
5. Debowska M., Swiatkowski W. and Wasolowski J., Acta Phys. Polon, 1977, # 51A, pp. 195-196.

6. Sen P. and Sen C., *Il Nuovo Cim.*, 1975, # 29B , pp. 124-127.
7. Hsu F.N., Shao J., Hulett L.D., Rosseel T.M. and Dale J.M., in *Positron Annihilation, ICPA-8*, World Scientific, Singapore, 1988, pp. 840-843.
8. Chang T., *Positron annihilation, ICPA-8*, World Scientific, Singapore, 1988, p. 150.
9. Sen P. and Patro A.P., *Il Nuovo Cim.*, 1969, # 64B, pp. 324-325.
10. Steld F.R. and Varlashkin P.G., *Phys. Rev. B*, 1973, # 7 , pp. 3394-3395.
11. Chang T.B., Deng J.K., Akahane T., Chiba T. and Kakimoto M., *Positron Annihilation, ICPA-7*, World Scientific, Singapore, 1985, pp. 974-976.
12. VenKateswaran K., Cheng K.L. and Jean Y.C, *J. Phys.Chem.*, 1984, # 88, pp. 2465-2469.
13. Kirkegaard P., Pedersen N.E. and Eldrup M., *PATFIT 88| A Data Processing System for Positron Annihilation Spectra on Main- frame and Personal Computers*, Denmark, Risom-2740, 1988.
14. Arifov P., Vasserman S. and Tishin S., *Phys. Stat. Sol.*, 1987, # 102a, pp. 565-568.
15. Arifov P., Vasserman S., Dontsov A., Tishin S. *Dokl. AN SSSR*, 1984, # 277, pp. 889-893.
16. Arifov P., Vasserman S., Tishin S. in *Positron Annihilation ICPA-7*, World Scientific Publishers, Singapore, 1985, pp. 787-790.
17. Tishin S., Tishin V. and Shipilevskiy B., *Plaste und Kautschuk*, 1991, # 2, pp. 45-51.